

Satisfaction of Patients on Health Care Services - A Study of Private Multi – Speciality Hospitals in Coimbatore District, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The main objective of the study is to examine the level of satisfaction of patients and the factors influencing their level of satisfaction on healthcare services provided by the Private Multi – Speciality hospitals in Coimbatore District of Tamil Nadu. Data were collected from both In- Patients and Out-Patients through pre-structured interview schedules. The level of satisfaction of the patients on healthcare services provided by the Private Multi – Speciality hospitals are evaluated and analyzed by “Multiple Regression Analysis” by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 22.0). The level of satisfaction towards services offered by the private multi-speciality hospitals is positively associated with their Occupational Status, Residential Area, Sources of Awareness, Health Facility Centre and Nature of Treatment in the study area. On the other hand, the co-efficient of Age, Educational Qualification and Marital Status are negatively associated. Hence, the management of the hospitals has to initiative suitable steps and measure to improve the level of satisfaction of the patients on the various quality aspects.

Keywords: Healthcare Services, Medical facility, Medical treatment, Competent Doctors, Patients expectations and Patients’ satisfaction.

Introduction

The level of satisfaction towards services offered by the Private Multi- Speciality hospitals has been measured on the basis of their opinion about their satisfaction factors, perceived against the variety of services offered by the hospitals in the following aspects. Level of satisfaction in general, registration services, room environment, supportive services, physicians competence and medical care, medicine facilities, care and services of the support staff, dietary and canteen services, hospital charges, safety provisions / hygienic conditions in the hospital, discharge process and billing system and post discharge / post treatment services.

Statement of the Problem

Healthcare services have a distinct position among the various services due to the highly involving and risky nature of it. While, the large number of public and private hospitals existing all over

the country, it is found that many government hospitals are not able to provide quality services to patients. Furthermore the private hospitals also are not able to fulfill the requirements of the patients to a certain extent. The main problem of hospitals is that they are not able to provide quality service based on the needs and expectations of the patients. One of the main problems is lack of adequate and timely medical treatment to patients. The other problems are non availability of medical facility, inadequate competent doctors, nurses and employees etc.

In this context, the researcher is interested in undertaking a study and an attempt is made to find out the Satisfaction of Patients' towards the healthcare services offered by private multi - speciality hospitals in Coimbatore District. Based on the issues stated above and development in healthcare services, the researcher has raised the following question.

1. What is the level of satisfaction of the patients towards the various facilities provided by the private multi- speciality hospitals?

In order to find out the answers for the above question, the researcher has undertaken the present study. It is hoped that the present study will contribute towards a better understanding of the healthcare services rendered by private multi - speciality hospitals in Coimbatore city.

Objectives of the Study

Based on the above issues, the study is to evaluate the level of satisfaction of patients on healthcare services provided by the Private Multi – Speciality hospitals in Coimbatore District of Tamil Nadu.

Research Methodology

Collection of Data

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. The primary data were collected from both in-patients and out patients of the hospitals through personal interview with the patients. For conducting the personal interview well framed interview schedule is prepared in a simple and understandable way so as to enable the patients to express their opinions freely and frankly. The interview is quite normal and in the natural conversational style and the data are recorded by the researcher in the interview schedule. In this process adequate care has been exercised to collect unbiased data. The secondary data were collected from the publication of reports, books and periodicals.

Field Work and Collection of Data

The field work for the study was conducted during the period from July 2017 to December 2017.

Sample Size

This study is based on Convenience Sampling method. Private Multi- Speciality hospitals having bedding strength of above 300 were selected for the study. Six such hospitals exist in Coimbatore District and are located in Coimbatore City. These six hospitals selected for the study are G.Kuppusamy Naidu Memorial Hospital (GKNMH), KG Hospital, Kovai Medical Center and Hospital (KMCH), Kongunad Hospital, PSG Hospital, Sri Ramakrishna Hospital.

Sample size was designed on the basis of sample size calculator using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Where,

n = Sample size

p = The probability value for 'p' is not known, if past information not available it can simply set the value of 'p' to 0.5.

q = (1 - p) = 0.5.

Z = Confidence level of 95%, with Z Value of 95% is 1.96

E = Tolerance level of error is 0.04, i.e., 4% of error is estimated.

$$N = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5) (1-0.5)}{(0.04)^2} = 600.25 \text{ i.e., } 600.$$

The sample size of 600 respondents (Patients) were selected from the above selected hospitals by applying Disproportional (Non- Proportional) sample size under stratified random sampling technique i.e., an equal number 100 respondents (Patients) have selected from each stratum (hospitals) regardless of their existence in the population. In all the six hospitals totally 600 patients have selected for the study.

Frame work of Analysis

The level of satisfaction of the patients on healthcare services provided by the Private Multi – Speciality hospitals are evaluated and analyzed by “Multiple Regression Analysis” by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 22.0).

Limitations of the Study

The study was conducted in Private Multi – Speciality hospitals in Coimbatore City of Tamil Nadu State and not those in Government or other sector, so the findings cannot be generalized to apply to all the patients in whole of Tamil Nadu State.

Results and Discussion: Level of Satisfaction towards Health Care Services of Private Multi-Speciality Hospitals - Multiple Regression Analysis

The level of satisfaction of patients and the factors influencing their level of satisfaction on healthcare services provided by the Private Multi – Speciality hospitals is evaluated by Multiple Regression Analysis. In this analysis, it has been selected eleven independent factors to analyze the strength of relationship between the levels of satisfaction among the sample patient respondents towards health care services offered by private multi-speciality hospitals in Coimbatore District.

The selected eleven independent factors are listed below

1. Age
2. Gender
3. Educational Qualification
4. Occupational Status
5. Monthly Income of the Family
6. Marital Status
7. Residential Area
8. Sources of Awareness
9. Health Facility Centre
10. Nature of Treatment
11. Kind of Admission

In order to measure the interdependence of independent factors and their level of satisfaction towards services offered by multi-speciality hospitals, the results were subjected to multiple regression analysis. The results of multiple regression analysis are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Level of Satisfaction towards Health Care Services of Private Multi-Speciality Hospitals - Multiple Regression Analysis

Sl. No.	Variables	Un standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	't' value	Sig.
		Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	1.204	0.187			
1	Age	-0.090	0.014	-0.296	-6.423	1%
2	Gender	0.016	0.029	0.023	0.535	NS
3	Educational Qualification	-0.060	0.022	-0.106	-2.707	1%
4	Occupational Status	0.119	0.043	0.121	2.768	1%
5	Monthly Income of the Family	0.007	0.024	0.010	0.266	NS
6	Marital Status	-0.029	0.011	-0.100	-2.656	1%
7	Residential Area	0.060	0.023	0.103	2.637	1%
8	Sources of Awareness	0.227	0.052	0.195	4.369	1%
9	Health Facility Centre	0.050	0.023	0.088	2.202	5%
10	Nature of Treatment	0.044	0.008	0.219	5.516	1%
11	Kind of Admission	0.025	0.015	0.071	1.662	NS

Source: Compiled from field data.

R-Value	R2 -Value	Degree of freedom – V1	Degree of freedom – V2	F Value	Significance
0.886	0.785	11	588	195.49	1% Level

The multiple linear regression co-efficient (dependent variable) is found to be statistically good fit as R2 is 0.785 for level of satisfaction towards health care services of private multi-speciality hospitals. It shows that independent variables contribute about 78.5 per cent of the variation in the level of satisfaction felt by the selected sample patients towards health care services of private multi-speciality hospitals and this is statistically significant at 1% level and 5% level respectively.

The resulted equation shows that level of satisfaction towards health care services of private multi-speciality hospitals is predicted by the -0.090 unit decrease of age, 0.016 unit increase of gender, -0.060 unit decrease of educational qualifications, 0.119 unit increase of occupational status, 0.007 unit increase of monthly income of the family, -0.029 unit decrease of marital status, 0.060 unit increase of residential area, 0.227 unit increase of sources of awareness, 0.050 unit increase of health facility centre, 0.044 unit increase of nature of treatment and 0.025 unit increase of kind of admission.

The table indicated that the co-efficient of Occupational Status, Residential Area, Sources of Awareness, Health Facility Centre and Nature of Treatment are positively associated with the

level of satisfaction. On the other hand, the co-efficient of Age, Educational Qualification and Marital Status are negatively associated. Further, it indicated that the contribution of Occupational Status, Residential Area, Sources of Awareness, Health Facility Centre and Nature of Treatment are statistically significant and implying that their level of satisfaction is stronger than the other variables.

Thus from the above analysis, the following observation could be made. The level of satisfaction towards services offered by the private multi-speciality hospitals is positively associated with their Occupational Status, Residential Area, Sources of Awareness, Health Facility Centre and Nature of Treatment in the study area.

Findings

It was found that out of eleven, eight factors were closely associated with the level of satisfaction towards services offered by the Multi-Speciality hospitals by the selected sample respondents.

Recommendations

It is concluded that the management of the hospitals has to initiative suitable steps and measure to improve the level of satisfaction of the patients on variables such as Age, Gender, Educational Qualifications, Monthly Family Income and Marital Status.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the hospitals has to keep in mind the mantra that “ Customer (i.e., Patients) is the King” and hospitals exist to serve them and should practice full range of services that fulfill patients expectations. It is hoped that the health care providers would pay more attention to quality in every aspect of patient care, both medical and non-medical services to satisfy the patients. As patient satisfaction is the valuable asset of the health care providers, understanding the patients’ problem and believing that it is most important, goes a long way towards the success of every health care providers.

References

Books

1. Nandagopal, R., et.al. *PSG Excel Series - Research Methods in Business*, First ed., PSG Institute of Management, New Delhi, 2007.
2. Services Marketing, S.M.JHA, Himalaya Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, Reprint 2010.
3. Services Marketing and Management, Dr.B.Balaji, S.Chand, New Delhi, Second Revised Edition: 2006, Reprint 2008.
4. Services Marketing, Vasati Venugopal, Raghu. V.N. *Himalaya Publishimng House*, Mumbai, First Edition: 2001, Reprint: 2006.
5. Services Marketing Concepts, Planning and Implementation, C. *Bhattacharjee – Excel Books*, New Delhi, First Edition: 2006.

Journals

1. Staniszewska S. Ahmed L (1998). Patient expectation and satisfaction with health care. *Nurs Stand*, 12 34-38.
2. Al- Ddghaither AH. Saced A A. Consumers’ satisfaction with primary health services in the city of Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Medical Journal* 2000; vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 447-454.
3. Kinsey J. Bradshaw P. Ley P. Patients satisfaction and reported acceptance of advice in general practice: *J.R.Gen Pract* 1975; 25: 558-566.

4. Roghmann K. Hengst A. Zastowny T. Satisfaction with medical care: its measurement and relation to utilization: Med Care 1979; 17: 461- 477.
5. Fitzpatrick R. Surveys of patient satisfaction. Important general considerations: Br Med J 1991; 302: 887-889.

Webliography

1. http://www.wikipedia.org/wiki.coimbatore_india#healthcare.
2. <http://www.indexmundi.com/facts>
3. www.skycrapercity.com
4. <http://www.medifee.com/list/best-hospitals-coimbatore>